

THE WORLD'S OLDEST ART

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Abstract. This article discusses the basics of new renaissance visual art, pen drawing, compositional painting methods of reflecting ideas and creative technologies in Uzbekistan.

Key words : pencil drawing , development, composition, fine art, type, genres.

Fine art is usually an art that expresses existence through certain forms or visible images. That is, it is reflected in space, on a surface or plane (on the surface of paper, wall surface, cloth, etc.) using forms.

The concept of fine art has a broad meaning, including graphics, painting and sculpture. All types are close to each other and have some similarities. However, each has its own characteristics, painting styles and techniques. At the same time, we can divide them into a number of types and genres, depending on their place of use, specific theme and style.

We will not be mistaken if we say that the fine and practical decorative art, architectural examples created by our ancestors are our monuments and a living and reliable mirror of our rich history. That is, all these were created by talented artists and artistically expressed based on the laws of beauty.

Works of art can express life, forms in visual arts, sounds in music, words in fiction, theater and cinema - synthesis of arts. Regardless of the form in which art is expressed, a certain idea is promoted in all of them. At first, it manifests itself in the influence of emotions and tone, and then it forms the perception of beauty. People develop aesthetic taste and enjoy all the beauties of life to a certain extent.

The creations created by artists have no borders. All people can enjoy the world of art equally, regardless of the nationality and territory of the creative works. Its wonderful secret is that it can always spread goodness in all regions. That is why there is always no harm coming from people who are creative in the field of art and people who enjoy other forms of art. Their hearts are to do good to others, to create works that give others aesthetic taste and mood.

The history of visual art of Uzbekistan is one of the integral parts of the history of world visual art, and it is one of the most ancient and widespread types of art. These unique creations of human thinking attract people to this day. In the territory of Uzbekistan, we can find ancient paintings. That is, through the wall paintings in Bolaliktepa, Varakhsha and Afrosiyab, we can understand the interest of our ancestors in fine arts and how beautiful they were. Even in the work of ancient artists, observation had a significant influence and was able to clearly describe the nature and content of events. All of these are different, and each character, shape, and design represents a unique idea and feature. Through this, we can see the important role of visual arts in their lives.

In fine art, there are monumental and easel forms, each with its own characteristics. Monumental is considered to be the example of visual art, which is large in terms of size, designed for architecture, avenue, garden and a certain artistic environment. covers the use of secret ceramics on the wall (mosaic) and similar directions. Monumental works serve to clearly see the image from a long distance.

Easel painting is considered to be one of the most widespread types of art in modern fine art. Usually, such pictures are made on canvases stretched on a specially made frame. An easel is a product of free creativity and activity. One of the funniest aspects of it is that we can put it where we want and display it. For example, the statues in the alleys are considered monumental works. If the sculpture is made according to the creator's own desire and creative search, and if

the aspects typical of works in this direction are realized, it can be placed in a museum or educational classrooms as a work of art. Easel painting, unlike monumental and decorative painting, is not directly connected to other types of art. Such paintings, in addition to reflecting important events and events, also have the ability to show a person's feelings, experiences, character and uniqueness. In this line, we can see the subtle changes taking place in nature, the beauty of nature, its diversity and its graceful aspects. All this is more likely to be quickly described and quickly presented to the public with a Yorkine expression.

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